

FATIGUE DAMAGE GROWTH CHARACTERIZATION OF CFRP COMPOSITES USING INTERNAL DAMPING MEASUREMENTS AND ACOUSTIC EMISSION MONITORING

L. Vellios, V. Kostopoulos and S. A. Paipetis

Applied Mechanics Laboratory, Department of Mechanical Engineering,
University of Patras, 265 00 Patras Greece.

ABSTRACT

Fatigue damage and failure mechanisms of Carbon/Epoxy composite materials were studied based on material damping measurements for different lamination geometries. The measurements of damping were performed by using the free vibrations of a cantilever beam at various stages of the fatigue procedure. A model relating damage with damping growth was used to provide a framework by which damage development was correlated to mechanical response. Damping growth, different for each eigenfrequency, in addition to eigenfrequency shifting, measured continuously during the course of cyclic loading, was shown to provide a reproducible and reliable tool for the characterization of the state of damage. Different material response could be associated with each laminate type uniquely, but for a given lamination geometry, it was found that three distinct regions in the material response during fatigue could be determined. Damage detection and characterization was accomplished by acoustic emission and the results were correlated with damping. The results were also supported analytically.

Keywords :

Composite materials, fatigue, damping, nondestructive evaluation, fracture mechanics, matrix cracks, delamination, fibre fracture.

1. INTRODUCTION

The extensive use of composite laminates in a wide range of applications, especially in critical components such as complete aircraft wing structures and fuselage, brings as top priority the requirement of reliability of these materials under low-level, long-term, variable-amplitude cyclic loading. Subcritical cyclic loading of composites is responsible for damage initiation and progressive development of all damage modes, which alter the state of the material and affect its life.

The amount of damage, the interaction of damage modes and damage accumulation, affect the stiffness, damping, strength and life of composite structures in a way depending on material system, stacking sequence, loading and environmental conditions. The challenge to establish a rational approach which can be used to answer the fundamental question of life prediction of a fatigue damaged composite, is always opened.

To this end, many investigations have been performed during the last decade, following the residual strength degradation [1,2] and modulus degradation [3-7] approaches, to predict fatigue life of

composites. The residual strength criterion uses mainly phenomenological characterization of the composite, in contrast to fatigue modulus degradation where it is based on understanding of the damage mechanisms involved in the fatigue process. Among them, Charewicz and Daniel [1] proposed a fatigue damage model based on the assumption that the strength degradation is a function of the life fraction n/N . A more advanced residual strength degradation model which can predict one and multi-stress level fatigue life has been proposed by Reifsnider et al [2]. In this work the strength degradation is a power function of fatigue cycles n , which is based on a local failure function and a microstructural analysis. On the other hand, evaluation of the fatigue damage development using stiffness reduction was proposed by O' Brien and Reifsnider [3] and Highsmith and Reifsnider [4]. In the keywork of Jamison et al [5] the stiffness reduction of multi-directional (MD) composites has been directly connected with mechanisms and the sequence of damage produced during the various stages of cyclic loading. Poursatip et al [6,7] proposed an analogue model based on fatigue modulus degradation and they calculate fatigue life using a strain failure criterion. Recently, a fatigue life prediction model was proposed by Han and Hwang [8], where a combination of modulus degradation and resultant strain failure criterion was used.

In the present work, the identification, characterization and analysis of damage events and mechanisms associated with cyclic loading of C/E laminates as a function of the number of cycles are presented based on the variation of material damping. Using a "stop and go" experimental procedure, a systematic and comprehensive study of damage development is given throughout the life of the specimen. In particular, the damping measurements were performed by exposing the fatigued specimen to a free flexural vibration within regular time intervals. Assuming that the composite laminate exhibits a viscoelastic response which follows the standard linear solid model, the specimen response was monitored and the acquisition of these results provided the specimen's eigenfrequencies and the relative damping coefficients. The proposed method is well supported by an analytical model which provides the necessary background of explanation of the damping coefficients appearing. This model is extensively described in Section 2. In Section 3 the experimental procedure is presented analytically and the obtained results for two different MD lamination geometries ($[0_2^\pm \pm 45^\circ, 0_2^\pm 90^\circ]$, and $[0_2^\pm \pm 30^\circ, 0_2^\pm \pm 60^\circ]$) are discussed extensively, together with the fatigue damage mechanisms involved in each stage of the experiment. In Section 4 results of the Acoustic Emission monitoring of the fatigue test are presented and correlated to the composite damage state and the relative damping measurements. Finally conclusions and indications for the application of the proposed technique on the fatigue life prediction of composite laminates are given in Section 5.

2. THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

Let a viscoelastic linear solid element be considered, which represents the macroscopic behaviour of a composite laminate of a specific lay-up sequence as appears in fig. 1. E_1 and E_2 are the elastic constants of the model and η is the internal damping coefficient. The constitutive relation for the model is given by

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dt} + \lambda\sigma = E \left(\frac{d\varepsilon}{dt} + \mu\varepsilon \right) \quad (1)$$

where σ and ε stand for the axial stress and strain respectively and the constants λ and μ exhibit the form

$$\lambda = \frac{E_1 + E_2}{\eta}, \quad \mu = \frac{E_2}{\eta}.$$

On the other hand, the flexural vibration of a beam is described by the partial differential equation (PDE)

Figure 1: 3-Parameter one dimension viscoelastic model

$$\frac{\partial^2 M(x,t)}{\partial x^2} = \rho A \frac{\partial w^2(x,t)}{\partial t^2} \quad (2)$$

where $M(x,t)$ is the bending moment at point x , for $t>0$,
 $w(x,t)$ the bending displacement at point x , for $t>0$
 ρ the mass density and A the cross section area

Figure 2: Single cantilever beam

Substituting in equation (2) the stress-displacement relation as well as the stress-bending moment equation and using the constitutive relation of the viscoelastic linear solid model, the following PDE is obtained, describing the flexural vibration of a composite beam with viscoelastic response according to the equation (1)

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^4} \left[\frac{\partial w(x,t)}{\partial t} + \mu w(x,t) \right] + \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \left[\frac{\partial^3 w(x,t)}{\partial t^3} + \lambda \frac{\partial^2 w(x,t)}{\partial t^2} \right] = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{where } \alpha^2 = \frac{EI}{\rho A}$$

In order to solve equation (3), one must know the boundary condition for the determination of the eigenfrequencies and the description of the initial conditions for the evaluation of the unknown coefficients of the solution. For a single cantilever beam with concentrated mass at the free edge (fig. 2) the following boundary conditions are assumed:

$$\text{For } x=0 : w(0,t) = 0 \quad (4), \quad \left. \frac{\partial w(x,t)}{\partial x} \right|_{x=0} = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{and for } x=L : M(L,t) = 0 \quad (6), \quad m \left. \frac{\partial^2 w(x,t)}{\partial t^2} \right|_{x=L} + Q(L,t) = 0 \quad (7)$$

where:

m is the concentrated mass due to the aluminum tabs of the vibrating specimen and the mass of the accelerometer

$M(L,t)$ the bending moment at $x=L$

$Q(L,t)$ the shear force at $x=L$

Assuming that the expression of bending moment and shear force with respect to flexural displacement is of the same type as in the case of perfectly elastic material, the solution of the problem of viscoelastic flexural vibration is provided by separation of variables for the PDE (3) and application of the above boundary conditions (4)-(7). The following spatial and time dependence of the solution is obtained

$$X_n(x) = \cos(k_n x) - \cosh(k_n x) + \frac{\sin(k_n L) - \sinh(k_n L)}{\cos(k_n L) + \cosh(k_n L)} (\sin(k_n x) - \sinh(k_n x)) \quad (8)$$

$$T_n(t) = A_n e^{d_n t} + e^{-\frac{d_n + \lambda_n}{2} t} (B_n \cos(\omega_n^d t) + C_n \sin(\omega_n^d t)) \quad (9)$$

where $k_n^4 = \frac{\omega_n^2}{\alpha^2}$ are the roots of the characteristic equation

$$\frac{m(kL)}{\rho AL} [\sin(kL) \cosh(kL) - \cos(kL) \sinh(kL)] - \cos(kL) \cosh(kL) - 1 = 0 \quad (10)$$

ω_n^d the eigenfrequencies of the viscoelastic flexural vibration problem and
 d_n a damping coefficient which is the negative real root of the frequency equation

$$s^3 - \lambda_n s^2 + \omega_n^2 s + \mu_n \omega_n^2 = 0$$

$$s_1^{(n)} = d_n < 0, \quad d_n \in R \quad \text{and} \quad s_{2,3}^{(n)} = -\frac{d_n + \lambda_n}{2} \pm i\omega_d^n$$

Finally the solution of the problem is obtained via the expression

$$w(x,t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n(x) T_n(t) \quad (11)$$

It is important to notice that the viscoelastic nature of the vibrating beam affects the time dependence of the solution only, while the spatial dependence is of the same form as with a purely elastic material.

In the following, the above model should be applied in an inverse way, where, from the measurements of the response of the composite beam in flexural vibration, the material properties could be evaluated. Due to the fatigue damage accumulation, the response of the vibrating specimen is different at each stage of fatigue process and by using the model, the material's characteristics are extracted as a function of the number of fatigue cycles.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Two multidirectional specimen groups were manufactured from Fibredux 914 C-TS-5-34% prepreg (CIBA-GEICY) material. The thickness was approximately 2 mm (16 layers). The stacking sequence was $[0_2^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, 0_2^\circ, 90_2^\circ]$, and $[0_2^\circ, \pm 30^\circ, 0_2^\circ, \pm 60^\circ]$, respectively. The dimension of the test coupons were according to ASTM standards for tensile and fatigue test (gauge length: 153 mm, width: 12.7 mm). Materials were subjected to tension-tension fatigue at a constant stress ratio $R = 0.1$ in a sinusoidal form at a cyclic frequency of 10 Hz in a servohydraulic, closed loop testing machine operating in the load-control mode. The maximum cyclic stress amplitude was 70% of the ultimate stress for each group of specimens. Each experiment follows the same steps: Initially, the virgin specimens were subjected to free vibration triggered by an initial displacement at the free end and the acceleration of the resulting vibration at the same point was measured (see fig.2). Then the specimens were subjected to tension-tension fatigue up to 10^6 cycles. At regular time intervals, corresponding to 5, 10, 20, 50, 100, 200, ..., 1000 thousand cycles the fatigue process was stopped and the specimen were exposed to a free flexural vibration. This was accomplished by opening the upper grip after stopping the test. Repetition of the same fatigue and free vibration boundary conditions was easy to secure in this way.

The measurements of acceleration were performed by using a 0.5 gr accelerometer with dynamic range of $\pm 500 g$ ($g = 9.81 m/s^2$) and sensitivity 3.46 mV/g. A data acquisition system was used to collect and store the analog amplified signal of the accelerometer. It was composed of an Analog-to-Digital (A/D) board, model A2000 of National Instruments (sensitivity: 2.5 mV, maximum sampling frequency: 1 MHz), connected on a Macintosh IIci computer. The A/D card was controlled through a data acquisition program code built on the environment of Lab VIEW 2. A typical output of these measurements is shown in fig.3.

The monitored signal (fig.3a) was analyzed, using a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) routine, in the frequency domain (fig.3b) in order to determine the eigenfrequencies of the vibrating composite beam. The time history of the transformed signal was gained using a Short FFT routine. Following this process the determination of the decay rate of each harmonic is concluded. Connecting the expected form of the beam's response under free vibration to the calculated data, the eigenfrequencies ω_d^n and the decay

Figure 3: a) Response of single cantilever beam to free vibration (acceleration measurement), b) Fast Fourier transform of acceleration

(4)

(6)

(5)

(7)

Figures 4,5: Normalized eigenfrequency and damping coefficient respectively versus number of fatigue cycles for $[0_2^{\circ}, \pm 45^{\circ}, 0_2^{\circ}, 90_2^{\circ}]_s$.

Figures 6,7: Normalized eigenfrequency and damping coefficient respectively versus number of fatigue cycles for $[0_2^{\circ}, \pm 30^{\circ}, 0_2^{\circ}, \pm 60^{\circ}]_s$.

lated data, the eigenfrequencies ω_n^0 and the decay exponents $-\frac{d_n + \lambda_n}{2}$, different for each eigenfrequency, are evaluated. This procedure was applied in the above stages of the fatigue procedure. The variation of both eigenfrequencies and damping coefficients plotted against loading cycles are presented in figs 4 : 7 for the lay-up sequences considered.

In fig.4 the variation of the first three normalized eigenfrequencies are plotted against the number of fatigue cycles for a $[0_2^{\circ}, \pm 45^{\circ}, 0_2^{\circ}, 90_2^{\circ}]_s$ laminate. In contrast to the first eigenfrequency which remains constant all over fatigue experiment, both the second and the third eigenfrequencies initially exhibit a rapid decrease during the first 10,000 cycles and after this stage follow a more smooth, almost linear decrease. Finally a third stage, with higher rate of decay, but short duration, arises after 700,000 cycles until the material fails. An analogous but more pronounced behaviour is exhibited by the dynamic flexural modulus of the material which are directly proportional to the root of the eigenfrequencies. In other words, all eigenfrequencies, but the first, as well as the relative dynamic flexural modulus, have a continuous variation as functions of fatigue cycles, in contrast to the relative results of the static test where the second region of the relative diagram (modulus of elasticity versus fatigue cycles) exhibits an almost constant value [5].

In fig.5 the variation of the normalized damping coefficients for the first three eigenfrequencies are plotted against the number of fatigue cycles. As it was expected the material damping increases with the increase of the fatigue cycles, or equivalently with the increase of the internal damage. For all the damping coefficient curves three different regions are distinguished as in the relative curves of figure 4. But now the damping coefficient of the first eigenfrequency is also affected by the fatigue damage. The most important difference between the relative curves of figures 4 and 5 is that the internal damage due to fatigue affects continuously and more drastically the damping coefficient than the relative eigenfrequencies. An other useful remark is that the initiation of the critical third stage is recognized earlier, using the curves of damping coefficient.

Figures 6 and 7 show the variation of the first four normalized eigenfrequencies and the variation of the relative damping coefficients respectively, versus the number of fatigue cycles for a

[$0, \pm 30, 0, \pm 60$], laminate. Two main differences appear during comparing these figures to the relative ones presented above and referring to the first laminate considered.

1. In both eigenfrequency and damping coefficient curves there is no initiation of the third region of damage area as it was described above. This agrees with the fact that no failure appeared after 10^6 cycles.

2. The values of the normalized damping coefficients in this case are lower compared to the above laminate and a possible explanation for this is the absence of 90° degree plies.

As a general observation, for both laminates considered, one should mention that the higher eigenfrequencies and their relative damping are affected more than the lower ones.

4. ACOUSTIC EMISSION MONITORING

In parallel to the "stop and go" procedure which was adopted for the characterization of damage state of the fatigued specimen, by measuring the eigenfrequency shifting and the relative damping, as described above, continuous Acoustic Emission (AE) monitoring was also performed. As well known, AE can be defined as elastic waves generated by a material subjected to an external stimulus. The AE technique focuses on rapid-energy-release events ranging in scale from the transient wave launched by the advancement of a subcritical crack all the way down to material readjustment due to cooperative movements between its constituents [9]. Monitoring of AE activity during a fatigue test may be a suitable means to provide information relevant to the mechanisms involved in the progress of material damage and the sequence by which they appear. Parameters leading to such characterization are the amplitude of the monitored signal, the duration of the separate events, the number of counts and the rise time (time needed to reach the peak). An overall estimation of the material damage may be obtained by following the behaviour of these parameters of the emitted signals, as well as their total energy, at discrete time intervals.

With a composite material, the evaluation and identification of the monitored signals to the specific damage modes is rather difficult as compared to homogeneous materials. In fact, there is a continuous background AE activity due to material friction. After the appearance of the first delaminated areas this activity grows up and covers events with low and medium amplitude.

In the present work, AE activity was monitored using Physical Acoustic Corporation apparatus (SPARTAN AT system), a computerized AE system that performs AE signal measurements and stores, displays and analyzes the resulting data. The AE signals are converted utilizing a 150 kHz transducer 15 mm diameter, preamplified and measured in Independent Channel Controller. The transducer was placed at the middle of the specimen's length, attached to the sample with a coupling agent (silicon gum) and then taped in place. The number of fatigue cycles and the load applied from the universal tester was also monitored by the SPARTAN AT system. Furthermore, using a triggering system, the monitoring of AE signals was performed only during the loading period of each fatigue cycle. A 60 db amplitude threshold was used. Concerning the fatigue conditions, these are identical to those described in Section 3. Observation of the signals analyzed allows for speculations of the nature of the events producing the emissions and on the emission expected during fatigue. Three sources appear possible at first sight:

(A) Matrix cracking, first appears in the off-axis plies parallel to the fibres direction and continuously in the 0° degree plies. The latter are few in number and small in length initially and they grow up slowly and stably with increasing number of cycles. The characteristics of such a damage emission are relatively low amplitude, large duration and short rise time of these events. Some initial high amplitude and increased duration and rise time events appearing during the first fatigue cycles are possibly produced by the grips and the relaxation of stress concentration due to discontinuities on a micro-scale level.

(B) Delaminations, mainly arising from the propagation of matrix cracks occurring in the off-axis laminae all the way through the thickness and their bridging with the longitudinal cracks, travels

(8)

(10)

(9)

(11)

Figures 8, 9, 10, 11: Amplitude, Duration, Risetime and Cumulative Energy cycles respectively of AE events versus the number of fatigue cycles.

parallel to the resin-rich interface of adjacent plies. The local moderate character of the initially appearing delaminations should be changed into a global one, as the saturation of the material with the matrix cracks in the longitudinal direction increases. The emissions in this case are of higher amplitude, large duration and increased rise time.

(C) Fibre breakage appears after the complete saturation of the matrix material due to the growth of longitudinal cracks, to the coalescence of delaminations associated with them and the development of longitudinal splitting [5]. At this stage the material failure is approaching. The AE signals are now of the burst type with high amplitude (close to 100db), small duration and short rise time.

At this point it is important to mention that, after the appearance of the first delaminations, a significant emission activity arises due to friction between adjacent plies. This activity increases along with material damage and is rich in amplitude, duration and rise time. In other words, after a critical number of cycles, different for each lay-up sequence, the emission due to friction covers all other types events. Only during fibre breakage the respective events can be distinguished again due to their high amplitude.

These remarks are clearly confirmed by the AE results. In figures 8-10 results for amplitude, duration and rise time respectively are plotted against the number of fatigue cycles in bar form for the $[0^\circ, \pm 30^\circ, 0^\circ, \pm 60^\circ]$ laminate. Finally, in figure 11 the cumulative energy of the signals emitted are plotted versus the number of fatigue cycles for the $[0^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ]$ laminate. In this curve, three distinct regions are exhibited providing a framework for the assessment of damage development and its directly correlation to the relative regions appearing in Section 3. Moreover, the initial state of figure 11 is one of rapid energy increase. This is followed by an intermediate region wherein the

energy remains almost constant with increasing fatigue cycles. The final stage is one of rapid increase, ending in specimen fracture. This bar-form diagram is in complete agreement to that of figure 5 presenting the variation of damping coefficients as a function of the number of fatigue cycles.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In the present work the characterization of the damage development of CFRP composites subjected to fatigue loading was performed both by using material damping measurements and acoustic emission monitoring. The fatigue damage produces a progressive eigenfrequency shifting, and this effect is more pronounced at the higher eigenfrequencies. Moreover, the relative damping coefficient for each harmonic increases with increasing number of fatigue cycles. Damping coefficients are much more sensitive towards fatigue damage than eigenfrequencies, and this fact can be used on a continuous basis to characterize the state of damage and, accordingly, for the evaluation of the remaining life of the relevant specimen or component.

Concerning AE techniques, the analysis of monitoring signals provides a powerful tool for life prediction by determining the critical point at which failure approaches. The main problems for the application of this technique in the characterization of fatigue damage is the huge amount of data that must be recorded and analyzed during the continuous monitoring and the high number of emitted events after the appearance of the first delaminations. A detailed investigation with different lay up sequences and of unidirectional composites are the obvious targets for future work.

Acknowledgment

The support by the General Secretariat for Research and Technology of the Ministry of Industry, Energy and Technology of Greece is gratefully acknowledged.

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